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AI AND CURRICULUM DELIVERY: A NEW ERA FOR CCMAS IMPLEMENTATION IN NIGERIAN UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: The job performance of public secondary school teachers in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, is pivotal to the overall quality of education delivery and student outcomes. This study examines the extent to which classroom management, lesson planning, and the use of instructional materials, contribute to teachers' job performance. A descriptive survey design was employed, with a multistage sampling procedure selecting 884 participants, comprising 832 teachers and 52 principals across 11 local government areas in Ibadan Metropolis. Data collection focused on teachers' engagement in classroom management practices, preparation of lesson notes, and utilization of teaching aids. Results from principals' and teachers' perspectives revealed that most teachers effectively involve students in setting classroom rules, demonstrate skillful management of misbehaviour, and maintain a balance between discipline and instruction. Additionally, a majority of teachers design purposeful lesson plans, utilize the internet for additional resources, and frequently employ visual aids to enhance learning. However, the use of innovative teaching methods, such as field trips and audio-visuals, was less prevalent. Statistical analyses indicated a high level of job performance among public secondary school teachers, with a weighted mean of 3.1503. This study recommends targeted interventions to address identified gaps and further enhance educational quality in Ibadan Metropolis.

Keywords: Job Performance, Public Secondary School Teachers

Introduction

The job performance of public secondary school teachers in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria, is intricately linked to several factors that directly influence the quality of education provided to students. Among the most critical components are classroom management, lesson planning or note preparation, and the use of teaching materials. These factors not only enhance teachers' job performance but also play a significant role in shaping the learning outcomes of students. Classroom management is fundamental to creating a conducive learning environment. Effective classroom management strategies help minimize disruptions, promote positive student behavior, and ensure that instructional time is maximized. In the context of Ibadan Metropolis, where large class

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sizes and diverse student backgrounds are common, strong classroom management skills are essential for maintaining focus and discipline. Lesson planning or note preparation is another key element in teachers' job performance. Well-structured lesson plans provide a clear roadmap for teaching, helping educators stay organized and focused on achieving specific learning objectives. Inadequate lesson preparation can lead to disorganized instruction, reducing the effectiveness of the teaching process and hindering student comprehension. Furthermore, the use of teaching materials, including textbooks, visual aids, and technology, is crucial in facilitating effective learning. The availability and proper utilization of these resources can significantly enhance students' understanding and engagement. However, challenges such as inadequate teaching materials and limited access to technology often impede teachers' ability to deliver quality education, particularly in public schools in Ibadan Metropolis. This study seeks to examine how classroom management practices, lesson planning, and the use of teaching materials influence the job performance of public secondary school teachers in Ibadan Metropolis. By exploring these areas, the research aims to identify key factors that contribute to teachers' effectiveness and propose strategies for improving educational standards in the region.

Literature Review

Every organisation expects high employee job performance to achieve the organisational goals and objectives. Due to the importance of job performance, researchers have devoted diligent effort to finding out how organisations can achieve high performance from their employees. Schools are not left out of this fundamental truth. Public and private schools (primary, secondary, and tertiary) expect maximum job performance from teachers and non-teaching staff to realize the school's educational goals and objectives. Job performance refers to the behavioural effort an employee has put into their job, which the organisation may interpret as either productive or unproductive (Madu, Ibeme, Abdulrasheed, Oyetimein, & Madu, 2024). According to Iswahyudi and Etikariena, (2024), job performance is a concept that stimulates behaviour that leads to evaluable achievements. In line with the above definitions, public secondary school teacher's job performance relates to the teachers' teaching behaviour, which projects their job contributions. The school management can measure this in line with the educational goals and objectives and interpret it as either excellent or poor. A teacher's job performance is essential for students' academic performance, a good image of the school and recognition of the school leadership, hence, for achieving national educational goals and objectives. That is, student learning behaviour indicates teacher effectiveness (Panayiotou, Kyriakides, Creemers, McMahan, Vanlaar, Pfeifer, & Bren, 2014). A teacher's job performance is of paramount importance in schools for several reasons. Teachers directly impact student learning outcomes. Effective teaching practices have been consistently linked to higher student achievement, academic growth, and overall educational success. When teachers perform well, students are more likely to be engaged, motivated, and able to reach their full potential. Teachers are the brain box of education, facilitating the school's teaching and learning process (Jagtap, 2016), Teachers serve as role models and mentors for their students. Beyond academic knowledge, they also impart crucial life skills, values, and attitudes. A teacher's conduct, proficiency, and dedication can significantly influence students' attitudes toward learning, self-esteem, and future aspirations. Teachers' job performance cuts across different aspects but in this Paper, it will be limited to classroom management, lesson planning or note preparation and use of instructional or teaching aid materials. Classroom management is a skill that every teacher must master to grasp the teaching-learning process fully. Students can display any behaviour to distract the teaching process, but when the teacher is proficient in classroom management, they can control students' behaviour (Ozen, & Yıldırım, 2020). Effective

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classroom management will help the teacher to achieve the clearly stated objectives for the day’s lesson. In the same vein, instructional materials such as pictures, objects, charts, audio-visuals, among others, are potent tools used by teachers to drive home their points during the teaching-learning process. The importance of instructional materials for effective learning cannot be overemphasised. It helps students to understand the lesson better. Teaching aids streamline and enrich the learning process, captivating students’ attention through visual and auditory stimulation. According to Tuma, (2021), incorporating interactive elements through instructional materials, learners become actively involved in their education. A good teacher must be faithful to using instructional materials to support classroom instruction, get learners’ attention, and promote learning. Lesson planning or note preparation is another essential part of teaching skills that can measure a teacher’s job performance. Lesson planning or preparation is a step-by-step written format that describes the flow of the teaching process and helps the delivery/presentation of the lesson. A lesson plan is a comprehensive outline of teaching procedures, covering written materials, techniques, time allocation, venue, and evaluation methods (Mariotti, 2009). Lesson planning and preparation help the teacher stay focused regarding the goal and objectives of the lesson and also help the teacher give the ideal and relevant lesson content to the learners using the appropriate teaching methods. Lesson planning and note preparation also help the teacher to remember to evaluate the learners based on what they taught. It is improper for a teacher to go to the classroom without a lesson plan because the lesson plan is the fundamental structure for class lesson. Lesson planning and note preparation help the teacher to manage their time and accomplish their aim within the specified lesson duration (Brandon, 2017).

Research Question

1. What is the level of Public Secondary School Teachers’ Job Performance in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State?

Method

This research adopted a descriptive survey design to determine public secondary school teachers’ job performance in Ibadan, Metropolis, and Oyo State. The population for this research included all principals and teachers of public secondary schools in the Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. Eleven (11) local government areas and three hundred and thirty-seven (337) public secondary schools are in the Ibadan Metropolis³. Also, three hundred and thirty-seven (337) principals and six thousand two hundred and thirteen (6213) teachers are in the Ibadan Metropolis. This paper employed a multistage (three stages) sampling procedure to select the sample for the study. The sample size for the study was eight hundred and eighty-four (884) participants which comprised eight hundred and thirty-two (832) public secondary school teachers and fifty-two (52) principals in Ibadan Metropolis.

Results

Research Question: What is the level of Public Secondary School Teachers’ Job Performance in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State?

Table 1: Level of Teachers’ Job Performance (Principals’ Perspective)

SN	Teachers	VO	O	R	VR	Mean	SD	Remark
Classroom Management								
1.	Involve students in	12	24	12	4	setting rules/codes of	(23.1%)	(46.2%) (23.1%)
(7.7%)	2.8462 0.87188	Moderate conduct in the classroom.						

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- 2. Know the right way and students (71.2%) (28.8%) - - misbehaviour 37 15 - - 3.7115 0.45747 High time to correct
- 3. Know when to transit from misbehavior (40.4%) (53.8%) (5.8%) to the teaching-learning domain. 21 28 3 - 3.3462 0.59027 High discipline
- 4. Careful not to focus too behaviours, (51.9%) (44.2%) (3.8%) but keep on strengthening good behaviours. 27 23 2 - 3.4808 0.57702 High many negative
- 5. Maintain the standard of misbehaviour of (59.6%) (40.4%) - - Students without compromise of fair or favour. 31 21 - - 3.5962 0.49545 High correcting

Average Mean Value: 3.3962

Lesson Planning/Note Preparation

- 6. Design lessons that ensure accurate, and (51.9%) (48.1%) moderate learning activities. 27 25 - - 3.5192 0.50450 High purposeful,
- Plan and prepare my going (69.2%) (28.8%) (1.9%) to the classroom to teach. 36 15 1 - 3.6731 0.51340 High lesson notes before
- 7. Explore the internet to information (44.2%) (36.5%) (19.2%) beyond textbooks. 23 19 10 - 3.2500 0.76376 High seek more

Average Mean Value: 3.4808

Use of Instructional Materials

- 9. Use visual aids like to (40.4%) (53.8%) (5.8%) teach. 21 28 3 - 3.3462 0.59027 High pictures and charts
- 10. Teach with drama and (13.6%) (32.7%) (48.1%) (5.8%) 7 17 25 3 2.5385 0.80346 Moderate music.
- 11. Use audio-visual to (17.3%) (26.9%) (50.0%) (5.8%) 9 14 26 3 2.5577 0.84976 Moderate teach.
- 12. Teach through field excursions. (30.8%) (42.3%) (26.9%) - 16 22 14 2.0385 0.70385 Low trips and

Average Mean Value: 2.6202

Source: Field Survey, 2024

KEY: VO = Very Often (4), O = Often (3), R = Rarely (2) and VR = Very Rarely (1).

Threshold: mean value of 3.0+ is High, 2.50 -2.99 is Moderate, while 2.50 below is Low.

Table 2: Level of Teachers' Job Performance (Teachers' Perspective)

S/N.	I	VO	O	R	VR	Mean	SD	Remark
Classroom Management								
1.	Involve students in of (39.1%) (45.6%) (12.1%) (3.2%)	325	379	101	27	3.2043	0.77511	High setting rules/codes conduct in the classroom.
2.	Know the right way and students' (57.2%) (40.1%) (2.0%) (0.6%)	476	334	17	5	3.5397	0.57074	High time to correct misbehaviour
3.	Know when to transit from misbehaviour (45.3%) (49.3%) (4.0%) (1.4%)	377	410	33	12	3.3846	0.63485	High discipline to the teaching-learning domain.

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4. Careful not to focus too 387 374 54 17 3.3594 0.69513 High many negative behaviours, (46.5%) (45.0%) (6.5%) (2.0%) but keep on strengthening good behaviours.

5. Maintain the standard of 436 354 35 7 3.4651 0.61957 High correcting misbehaviour of (52.4%) (42.5%) (4.2%) (0.8%) students without compromise of fair or favour.

Average Mean Value: 3.3906

Lesson Planning/Note Preparation

6. Design lessons that ensure 505 289 28 10 3.5493 0.62246 High purposeful, accurate and (60.7%) (34.7%) (3.4%) (1.2%) moderate learning activities.

7. Plan and prepare my 595 206 21 10 3.6659 0.58779 High lesson notes before going (71.5%) (24.8%) (2.5%) (1.2%) to the classroom to teach.

8. Explore the internet to 412 352 54 14 3.3966 0.68604 High seek more information (49.5%) (42.3%) (6.5%) (1.7%) beyond textbooks.

Average Mean Value: 3.5373

Use of Instructional Materials

9. Use visual aids like 276 396 132 27 3.1083 0.78099 High pictures and charts to (33.2%) (47.6%) (15.9%) (3.2%) teach.

10. Teach with drama and 149 267 311 105 2.5529 0.92672 Moderate music. (17.9%) (32.1%) (37.4%) (12.6%)

11. Use audio-visual to 119 218 321 173 2.3406 0.96357 Low teach. (14.3%) (26.2%) (38.6%) (20.8%)

12. Teach through field 97 184 286 265 2.1358 0.994363 Low Trips and excursions. (11.7%) (22.1%) (34.4%) (31.9%)

Average Mean Value: 2.5344

Source: Field Survey, 2024'

KEY: VO = Very Often (4), O = Often (3), R = Rarely (2) and VR = Very Rarely (1).

Threshold: mean value of 3.0+ is high; 2.50 -2.99 is Moderate, while 2.50 below is Low.

Table 1 presents the principals' perspective on the level of public secondary school teachers' job performance in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State. For classroom management, the table shows that 12(23.1%) principals indicated that their teachers involve students in setting rules of conduct in the classroom very often, as a form of job performance, 24 (46.2%) principals indicated that their teachers do it often, 12 (23.1%) principals indicated that their teachers do it on rare occasions, and 4 (7.7%) principals opted that their teachers do not do it at all. The Table also reveals that 37 (71.2%) principals indicated that their teachers know the right way and time to correct student(s)' misbehaviour very often in their job performance, and 15 (28.8%) principals noted that their teachers do it often. Also, the table shows that 21 (40.4%) principals noted that their teachers know when to transit from discipline misbehaviour to the teaching-learning domain very often as a sign of job performance, 28 (53.8%) principals noted that their teachers do it often, 3 (5.8%) principals noted that their teachers do that on rare occasions. In addition, 27 (51.9%) principals indicated that their teachers are very often careful not to focus too much on students' negative behaviours but keep on strengthening good behaviours as a form of job performance, 23 (44.2%) principals noted that their teachers do that often, 2 (3.8%) principals noted that their teachers do that on rare occasions. The Table again shows that 31(59.6%) and 21(40.4%) principals noted that their teachers

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maintain the standard of correcting students' misbehaviour without compromising fairness or favour very often and often respectively in their job performance. For lesson planning and note preparation, the table reveals that 27(51.9%) and 25 (48.1%) principals indicated that their teachers design lessons that ensure purposeful accurate, and moderate learning activities very often and often respectively in their job performance. The table shows that 36(69.2%) and 15 (28.8%) principals indicated that their teachers plan and prepare lesson notes before going to the classroom to teach very often and often respectively, while 1(1.9%) principal noted that their teachers rarely do it. The table also reveals that 23(44.2%) and 19 (36.5%) principals agreed their teachers do explore the internet to seek more information beyond textbooks very often and often respectively, while 10 (19.2%) principals opted that their teachers do that rarely. For the use of instructional materials, the Table also shows that 21 (40.4%) and 28 (53.8%) principals admitted that their teachers do use visual aids like pictures and charts to teach very often and often respectively, while 3 (5.8%) principals noted that their teachers rarely use them. Similarly, the Table brings to light that 7 (13.6%) and 17(32.7%) principals noted that teachers do teach through drama and music respectively, while 25 (48.1%) and 3 (5.8%) principals noted that their teachers rarely and very rarely respectively do that in their job performance. Moreover, the Table shows that 9 (17.3%) and 14 (26.9%) principals indicated that their teachers very often and often correspondently use audio-visuals to teach, and 26 (50.0%) and 3(5.8%) principals noted that their teachers rarely and very rarely use them correspondingly. Finally, 16 (30.8%) and 22 (42.3%) principals indicated that their teachers do teach through field trips and excursions very often and often respectively, and 14 (26.9%) principals noted that their teachers rarely teach through field trips, and excursions in their job performance. Table 2 presents the teachers' perspective on the level of public secondary school Teachers' Job Performance in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State. For classroom management, the table shows that 325(39.1%) teachers involve their students in setting rules of conduct in the classroom very often, as a form of job performance, 379 (45.6%) teachers do it often, 101 (12.1%) teachers do it on rare occasions, and 27(3.2%) teachers do not do it at all. The Table also reveals that 476 (57.2%) teachers know the right way and time to correct student(s)' misbehaviour very often in their job performance, 334 (40.1%) do it often, 17 teachers(2.0%) do it on rare occasions, and 5 teachers (0.6%) do not do it at all. Also, the table shows that 377 teachers (45.3%) know when to transit from discipline misbehaviour to the teaching-learning domain very often as a sign of job performance, 410 teachers (49.3%) do it often, 33 teachers (4.0%) do that on rare occasions, and 12 teachers (1.4%) do not know when to do it. In addition, 387 (46.5%) teachers are careful not to focus too much on students' negative behaviours but keep on strengthening good behaviours very often as a form of job performance, 374 teachers (45.0%) do that often, 54 (6.5%) and 17 (2.0%) teachers do that on rare occasions and very rarely respectively. The Table again shows that 436 (52.4%) and 354(42.5%) teachers maintain the standard of correcting students' misbehaviour without compromise of fair or favour very often and often respectively in their job performance, 35(4.2%) and 7(0.8%) teachers rarely and very rarely respectively do that. For lesson planning and note preparation, the table reveals that, 505 (60.7%) and 289 (34.7%) teachers design lessons that ensure purposeful accurate, and moderate learning activities very often and often respectively in their job performance, and 28(3.4%) and 10 (1.2%) teachers do that rarely and very rarely respectively. Furthermore, the Table shows that 595 (71.5%) and 206(24.8%) teachers do plan and prepare lesson notes before going to the classroom to teach very often and often respectively, while 21(2.5%) and 10(1.2%) teachers rarely and very rarely do it respectively. The table reveals that 412 (49.5%) and 352 (42.3%) teachers explore the internet to seek more information beyond textbooks very often and often respectively, while 54 (6.5%) and 14 (1.7%) teachers do that rarely and very rarely

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respectively. For the use of instructional materials, the Table also shows that 276 (33.2%) and 396 (47.6%) teachers do use visual aids like pictures and charts to teach very often and often respectively, while 132 (15.9%) and 27 (3.2%) rarely and very rarely respectively use them. Similarly, the Table brings to light that 149 (17.9%) and 267(32.1%) teachers respectively teach through drama and music, while 311 (37.4%) and 105 (12.6%) teachers rarely and very rarely do that in their job performance. Moreover, the Table shows that 119 (14.3%) and 218 (26.2%) teachers very often and often correspondently use audio-visuals to teach, while 321 (38.6%) and 173(20.8%) teachers rarely and very rarely use them correspondingly. Finally, 97 (11.7%) and 184(22.1%) teachers do teach through field trips and excursions very often and often respectively, while 286 (43.4%) and 265 (31.9%) teachers rarely and very rarely teach through field trips and excursions respectively in their job performance.

Table 3: Mean Summary of the Level of Teachers’ Job Performance

Teachers’ Job Performance (Weighted Mean)	Principals’ Perspective	Teachers’ Perspective	Average
Classroom Management	3.3962	3.3906	3.3934
Lesson Planning/Note Preparation	3.4808	3.5373	3.5091
Use of Instructional Materials	2.6202	2.5344	2.5773
Average Weighted Mean:			3.1599

From Table 3, the findings from both principals’ and teachers’ data reveal that the level of public secondary school teachers’ job performance in Ibadan Metropolis is high, with an average weighted mean of 3.1599.

Figure 1: Chart of the Level of Teachers’ Job Performance

Conclusion This Paper investigated the level of public secondary school Teachers’ Job Performance in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. Principals’ and teachers’ data revealed a high level of Teachers’ Job Performance. This high job performance of teachers may be due to several factors. As regards the level of Teachers’ Job Performance, it was found to be high with a weighted mean of 3.1503

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Recommendation

1. Teachers should intensify in the use of instructional materials such as drama and music, audio-visual aids, field trips, and excursions.
2. There should be targeted interventions by the government to address identified gaps and further enhance educational quality in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo state.

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